

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING CLINICAL SCIENCES IN E- LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of electron, information and communication and the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching Clinical Sciences in medical higher education institutions. The article covers electronic educational technologies, information and pedagogical technologies, integration, the meaning of integrated education and their content.*

Keywords: *medical education, future doctors, Information Technology, electronic educational technology, communication, integration, integrated education, switching, electronic resources.*

Introduction. The use of computers in the course of the lesson creates new and unique conveniences for teachers and students related to interactive teaching aids. Knowing modern programming languages for interactive teaching aids created by the teacher, it is necessary to achieve their acceptance by students with interest. The operative combination of computers with other educational tools, such as projectors, electronic boards, and the use of visual aids increases the volume of information giving and thus creates an opportunity for the teacher to use the class time effectively. Today, using the capabilities of modern programming languages, i.e. Delphi, Matlab, MathCad, Maple, Mathematica, Cilar, organizes the teaching process in a qualitative manner. As a result, the effectiveness of the lesson increases and the interest and attitude of students change. Improving the quality of teaching in education depends on how to use new teaching methods. In new teaching methods, the student should be constantly searching and moving, that is, he should receive the given information, process it and apply the acquired knowledge to solve specific problems. The application of information technologies in the form of lectures, practice, laboratory and independent education gives its results quickly. For example, the use of virtual stands in a laboratory lesson is the basis for the quality organization of the training. The unprecedented development of computers and software products opens wide opportunities for the use of information technology in education. Educational materials can be prepared in the form of multimedia systems and made available to the public through computer networks and transmission media. The widespread introduction of computer technologies into the educational system requires a revision of the educational materials of all types of education. It is necessary to prepare multimedia electronic educational materials in accordance with each form of education. In the context of today's information-saturated society and borderless information exchange, the issue of the erudition and mediation of future doctors is of paramount importance. It is known that it is in the hands of young people to further raise the future, prospects and prosperity of any state or society. But different spoiler it is not difficult to bring to the eyes what kind of morality a state, society or family can fall into the hands of young people who are watered with the ideology of fanaticism, who are part of the currents. Therefore, we believe that it is necessary for educators, parents to have a competence in media-literacy so that we can protect young people from the

destructive vices mentioned above. We are talking about this "modern computers or cellular communication to our young people not taking away tools or allowing them to access social sites should not be put", we do not want to say so.

Research Methodology. The mechanism for the formation of media-literacy skills in future doctors on the basis of step-by-step self-analysis will consist of:

1. Determination of the need for information. In this situation, students choose from the media stream what information they need based on their professional activities. It analyzes what kind of problem the information you are looking for can help to solve.

2. Identification of sources of information. In doing so, students determine from which sources they receive the information they need (Internet information, e-books, television). After sorting these sources, it will now separate the information into primary, secondary or tertiary sources, according to its sources.

3. Identification and search for information address. The future doctor will determine from which address he received the information he needs, and from which address is it better to look for the information, who needs to apply for help.

4. Analysis of the quality of information. Determination of information reliability and veracity. And for this, the student needs sufficient knowledge and qualifications. In turn, future doctors should be aware of the democratic processes taking place in society and in social life. Information from which sources is close to reality, and information from which sources is similar to falsehood, i.e. fake messages. Analyzes, sorts out this information obtained, gives an idea of which information quality is close to the current one.

5. Sorting information. Students will have to effectively organize information from several sources. Usually the sources that are disseminating information are not always disseminating the correct information.

Conclusion. Problems arise in the training and retraining of qualified medical personnel among the graduates of the higher medical educational institution. In this case, the first logical solution is computer-assisted education. With this, S.F. Sergeev said that after graduating from a higher medical educational institution, doctors, first of all, will develop as specialists in their field, and they will not have enough knowledge in the field of electronic education. He mentions the need to start training and retraining of personnel in the field of education. [85] (Sergeev S.F., 2015). In e-learning, the methods of e-learning development are also seen in the involvement in the educational process, which Nabi Y.A. showed in his works as follows: "Systematic approach. The systematic approach is determined by the use of the tools of the general theory of the system. In general, a systematic approach forms the basis of the methodology. This method can also be considered as a method of creating innovative systems. A dialectical approach. The dynamic character of the processes taking place in the educational process is the result of the continuous striving of the subjects of the educational process to improve, to move from the old to the new.

As a result of the above-mentioned scientific research, it is possible to consider the following aspects of the e-learning methodology:

1. General issues of electronic education. In this, the issues that form the basis of electronic education are considered. They include the following issues: pedagogical issues, technological issues, pedagogical design, purpose of pedagogical design, features of pedagogical design.

2. Process approach to e-learning. It shows the process of creating electronic education and its pedagogical foundations. They include: process model, pedagogical design of process approach.

3. Training of teachers. The activities and professional training of teachers play an important role in the organization of electronic education.

4. Forms of organization of electronic education. The following forms of organization of electronic education can be distinguished: lecture, practical training, organization of independent education.

5. Active methods of electronic education. In this, active methods of organizing electronic education are considered. They include: a general systematic view of pedagogical activity, active methods of e-learning, methodological guidelines for conducting webinars.

6. Use of multimedia in electronic education. In this, the areas of multimedia application are considered as important aspects of the organization of electronic education.

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